

HISTOPATHOLOGICAL LESION OF GALL BLADDER MUCOSA ASSOCIATED WITH CHOLELITHIASIS

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ABSTRACT

Aims & Objectives: To study the various changes in gall bladder mucosa in those gall bladder specimens who possesses gall stones and compare and correlate the data with the similar studies done in the past in different part of India.

Material & Methods: It is a hospital based study done in Santosh Medical College and Hospital, Ghaziabad. The duration of this study was 2 years. Total 131 open cholecystectomy specimens with complete gallstones were examined. We included male and female patients of all the age group. Patient of cholelithiasis diagnosed by radiology and recommended for cholecystectomy formed the study population. Autolysed cholecystectomy specimens and cholecystectomy specimens without gallstone were excluded from this study.

Results: We found that maximum number of specimens had chronic cholecystitis 97.7 %, followed by Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses 22.9%, muscular hyperplasia 15.3%, epithelial hyperplasia 8.4%, fibrosis and ulceration 3.8%, carcinoma 3.1%, antral metaplasia 2.3%, xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis 2.3%, eosinophilic cholecystitis and intestinal metaplasia each presented with 0.8%. In our study, carcinoma was always present with pigment type stone.

Conclusion: Carcinoma of gallbladder was found in (3.10%) cases which is higher ever reported in India. With the advancement of investigational procedures, more cases related to gallbladder pathologies have come to light, thus making it very much relevant to pursue a research in this field. Moreover, this study will bring forth to light the knowledge which will be advantageous to the population, dieticians as well as medical practitioners.

Keywords: Cholelithiasis, cholecystectomy, adenocarcinoma, histopathology.

INTRODUCTION

Gallbladder (cholecyst/biliary vesicle) is a flask shaped blind-ending, hollow viscus which is grey-blue in colour. It mainly serves as reservoir of bile, concentration of bile (5 to10 times), emulsification and absorption of fats and elimination of bilirubin which is a product of hemoglobin metabolism. Gall bladder presents mainly 3 layers. The innermost layer is mucosa having lining epithelium of single layer of tall columnar cells (apical microvilli, basal nuclei, lightly stained cytoplasm) [1], smaller pencil cells (darkly staining columnar cells) and basal cells. Lamina propria is made of loose connective tissue, fenestrated capillaries, small vessels nerves, some

diffuse lymphatic tissue and IgA containing plasma cells [2]. Second layer is muscular with large amount of elastic fibers intermingled with smooth muscle fibers, which are arranged in circular, longitudinal and oblique manner so this layer is also known as fibromuscular layer. Outer layer is serosa which covers its entire surface except the hepatic, where an adventitia attaches it to the liver. The gallbladder has a wide layer of perimuscular loose connective tissue which contain blood vessels, lymphatics and nerves.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS

This hospital based study was done in Santosh Medical College and Hospital Ghaziabad. The duration of this study was 2 years. The study was done in total 131 open cholecystectomy specimens with complete gallstones. The study included male and female patients of all the age groups. Patients of cholelithiasis diagnosed by radiology and recommended for cholecystectomy formed the study population. Autolysed cholecystectomy specimens and cholecystectomy specimens without gallstone were excluded from this study. For the detail microscopic examination of specimen routine histology technique (H&E staining) was used. Equipments used in the study were automatic tissue processor, semiautomatic embedding centre, rotary microtome, high and low profile blade, floatation (water) bath, slide drying oven / hot plate and binocular microscope.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Out of 131 open cholecystectomy specimens, maximum number had chronic cholecystitis 97.7 %, followed by Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses 22.9%, muscular hyperplasia 15.3%, epithelial hyperplasia 8.4%, fibrosis and ulceration 3.8%, carcinoma 3.1%, antral metaplasia 2.3%, xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis 2.3%, eosinophilic cholecystitis and intestinal metaplasia each presented with 0.8% (Table 1, Fig. 1). In our study, carcinoma was always present with pigment type stone.

Table 1: Percentage incidence of mucosal changes in cholecystectomy specimens

Parameter	No. of cases	Percentage
Chronic Cholecystitis	128	97.7%
Xanthogranulomatus cholecystitis	3	2.3%
Eosinophilic Cholecystitis	1	0.8%
Intestinal metaplasia	1	0.8%
Antral metaplasia	3	2.3%
Muscular hyperplasia	20	15.3%
Epithelial hyperplasia	11	8.4%
Carcinoma	4	3.1%
Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses	30	22.9%
Fibrosis & Ulceration	5	3.8%

Fig.1: Bar chart showing the incidence (%) of microscopic findings of mucosal changes in cholecystectomy specimens

H & E staining was done for the detail microscopic examination. Specimens of chronic cholecystitis showed disrupted epithelium, infiltrated lymphocytes and plasma cells, lymphoid follicles and Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses (Fig. 2). Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis was usually associated with chronic cholecystitis in 66.66% cases and depicted occluded Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses, mixture of infiltrated foamy histiocytes, lymphocytes, fibroblast, giant cells and multinucleated foreign body (Fig. 3). Antral metaplasia exhibited goblet cells, lymphocytes and glandular structures (Fig. 4). There was increase in thickness of fibromuscular layer in muscular hyperplasia of gall bladder specimens (Fig. 5). Specimens with epithelial hyperplasia of gall bladder presented increase lymphocytes and hyperplastic epithelium (Fig. 6). Carcinoma of gall bladder showed abnormally formed glandular structure lined by malignant epithelial cells i.e. hyperchromatid nuclei with variable shape and size of cells, infiltrated into stroma and tumor tissue is moderately differentiated (Fig. 7).

Fig. 2: Photomicrograph showing chronic cholecystitis of gall bladder as seen in H & E staining (B-40x). Disrupted epithelium (yellow arrow), infiltrated lymphocytes & plasma cells (red arrow), lymphoid follicles (purple arrow) and Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses (green arrow).

Fig. 3: Photomicrograph showing xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis of gall bladder as seen in H & E staining (B- 40x). Green arrow showing occluded Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses whereas red arrow showing mixture of infiltrated foamy histiocytes, lymphocytes, fibroblast, giant cells and multinucleated foreign body.

Fig. 6: Photomicrograph showing epithelial hyperplasia of gall bladder as seen in H & E staining (A-10x and B-40x). Yellow arrow- lymphocytes, blue arrow- hyperplastic epithelium, red arrow- Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses.

Fig. 4: Photomicrograph showing antral metaplasia of gall bladder as seen in H & E staining (A-10x). Yellow arrow representing goblet cells, red arrow lymphocytes and blue arrow glandular structures.

Fig. 7: Photomicrograph showing carcinoma of gall bladder as seen in H & E staining (A- 10x). Section from the growth of gallbladder shows abnormally formed glandular structure (red arrow) lined by malignant epithelial cells (yellow arrow- hyperchromatic nuclei with variable shape and size of cell), infiltrated into stroma, tumor tissue is moderately differentiated.

Fig. 5: Photomicrograph showing muscular hyperplasia of gall bladder as seen in H & E staining (A-10x). Blue arrow showing thickness of fibro-muscular layer.

DISCUSSION

In the present study it was observed that the most common histopathological change in mucosa of gallbladder associated with cholelithiasis is chronic cholecystitis which is followed by Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses, muscular hyperplasia, epithelial hyperplasia, fibrosis and ulceration, carcinoma, antral metaplasia, xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis, eosinophilic cholecystitis and intestinal metaplasia.

In the present study the most common finding was chronic cholecystitis reported in 97.7% cases. This fact

is supported by some previous studies [3-5], but it is in contradiction to other studies [6-8]. Maximum percentage of incidence of chronic cholecystitis was reported by Zahrani and Mansoor 97% [9], whereas minimum by Jain et al. who reported it to be 30.50% [10]. In maximum cases chronic cholecystitis is associated with Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses.

The second most common finding was the presence of Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses, which was present in 30 (22.90 %) cases. The presences of Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses have been also reported by previous studies done in different parts of world in different time period. Zuhair and Mumtaz reported 33.2 % [11], Kaur et al. 44.80 % [12] and Terada et al. 65 % cases [13] in their studies.

In present study incidence of muscular hyperplasia was found in 20 (15.30 %) cases. This finding is very much coincides with that of Hamdani et al. [14], but contradicts by some other studies [9,15,16].

In present research work, epithelial hyperplasia was noted in 11 (8.40 %) cases. Epithelial hyperplasia was also reported by other researchers although in much higher percentage [11,16-18].

The incidence of xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis was found in 3 (2.30%) cases. Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis was usually associated with chronic cholecystitis in 66.66% cases. It usually occurs when occluded Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses rupture. This fact was supported by other studies also [1,8], but Kaur et al. reported very low 1.04% incidence [12] whereas Khan et al. reported highest 3.6% incidence [5].

In the present study, carcinoma of gallbladder was found in 4 (3.10%) cases. Gallstones appear to be the most important risk factor, being reported in 70-98% cases of gallbladder cancer, a far higher prevalence than that in age-matched general population [19]. Gallstones are responsible for generating a series of epithelial histopathological changes which may act as precursor of lesions of gallbladder cancer. Incidence of carcinoma of gallbladder found is nearly similar to some previous studies [3,4,6], but contradict the studies done by Khanna et al. [16] and Zahrani and Mansoor [9] who reported a very low incidence 0.7 % and 1% respectively.

A rare eosinophilic cholecystitis was observed in only 1 (0.80 %) case of all cholecystectomy specimens in our study which is comparable with that of some previous studies [4,5,8].

Metaplastic changes were present in total 4 cases (3.10 %) of which antral metaplasia was more frequent seen in 3 (2.30%) cases, followed by intestinal metaplasia which was observed in only 1 (0.80 %) case. Incidence of intestinal metaplasia was very low in present study in comparison to other studies, but it is in agreement with the study done by Jain et al. [10] who has reported 2.5 % incidence but is in contradiction with other studies[12,17,18]. Incidence of antral metaplasia was also very less in present study as compared to previous studies [10,12,16].

Fibrosis occurred in 5 (3.8 %) cases in present research. Fibrosis of gall bladder has been reported by other studies also but the reported prevalence was very high in these studies [16,20] in comparison to present study.

CONCLUSION

Carcinoma of gallbladder was found in (3.10%) cases which is higher ever reported in India. In this study it was observed that the carcinoma of gallbladder mainly occurs in elderly individuals but it may be present in young persons also. Presence of gallstones is the most important risk factor in case of gallbladder cancer. Gallstones are responsible for generating a series of epithelial changes which may act as precursor of gallbladder cancer. The incidence of carcinoma is increased in the last two decades due to migration of large number of people for searching job opportunity in cities (urbanization) and has changed their food habits, culture and environment. Excessive use of junk food, increase amount of fat, refined carbohydrates, decrease dietary fibers and physical exercise is an important risk factor for formation of gallstones.

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